

1 **Integrated Hydrological Model and GIS-based Model to Map Landslides Risks within the**
2 **Anacostia Watershed of Maryland**

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1 **ABSTRACT**

2 Landslides are significant geological hazards that cause extensive damage to property, infrastructure, and
3 human life. This study investigates the impact of rainfall infiltration on landslide susceptibility within the
4 Anacostia River watershed in Maryland, USA. Utilizing the Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT+),
5 we modeled the entire hydrological cycle to simulate rainfall infiltration and runoff. Subsequently, a GIS-
6 based model was developed to map the minimum amount of infiltrating water (F_{min}) that will cause slope
7 failure and assess landslide risk using infiltration data derived from SWAT+. The study area was chosen
8 due to more records of historical landslides, and available detailed climate, soil, and land use data for
9 accurate model calibration. The SWAT+ model demonstrated high accuracy, with NSE and Pbias values
10 indicating good performance. The GIS-based model successfully highlighted areas with varying landslide
11 risks, providing a comprehensive assessment of potential landslide-prone zones. Our findings emphasize
12 the critical role of water infiltration in slope stability and offer a robust framework for landslide risk
13 management in regions susceptible to heavy rainfall.

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16 **Keywords:** Landslide, Infiltration, Hydrological model, Landslide risk mapping.

1 INTRODUCTION

2 Landslides are one major geological hazard that may seriously harm property, infrastructure, and
3 even human life (1). Landslides occur in all 50 states and territories, and they affect lives, property,
4 infrastructure, and the environment (2, 3). Accumulation landslides are prone to occur during the continuous
5 infiltration of heavy rainfall, which seriously threatens the lives and property safety of residents (4).
6 Landslides occur in all parts of the United States and cause \$1-2 billion in damages and more than 25
7 fatalities on average each year (5). According to the International Disaster Database of the Centre for
8 Research on the Epidemiology of Disasters since 1900 some 130,000 people have lost their lives because
9 of landslides and flash floods; and the economic losses amounted to over US\$ 50 billion (6).

10 The interaction between soil properties and water infiltration is a major factor that affects the
11 frequency and severity of landslides (7, 8). Heavy or continuous rainfall often triggers regional-scale
12 widespread shallow landslides (9, 10, 11, 12). Water seeping into the soil can cause instability on slopes by
13 lowering the soil's shear strength and raising the moisture content of the soil (13, 14, 15, 16, 17). The
14 addition of water from rainfall or snow melting could increase the driving force and create seepage forces
15 along the slope (18, 19, 57).

16 Wu et al. (20) found that the preferential seepage flow through tension cracks at the slope crest
17 causes the failure when it reaches the bedrock surface, and it is easier for the soil slope to slide along the
18 interface between soil and bedrock than along the wetting front. According to previous studies, with the
19 loss of suction, the effective stress of the soil decreases, and the additional shear strength provided by the
20 negative pore water pressure will be lost. Therefore, suction is also important for slope stability (21, 22, 23,
21 24). Rainfall infiltration can cause a dramatic decrease of suction in unsaturated soils and, consequently, of
22 shear strength, triggering various instability phenomena, such as the slip of steep surface soil layers (25).
23 Given Maryland's varied soil types and heavy rainfall, one of the main factors influencing the state's
24 susceptibility to landslides is water infiltration.

25 Many studies have investigated the slope instability risk by considering infiltration. Chiu et al. (26)
26 developed an in-house physical-process-based shallow landslide model to investigate the influence of
27 runoff. The model couples the shallow water equation (dynamic) with Richards' equation. By applying an
28 infinite slope stability analysis, they evaluated the potential for regional landslides. Using a real catchment
29 topography as an example, the simulation revealed variations in runoff and the factor of safety (FS) during
30 storms. Dolojan et al. (27) developed a method to analyze shallow slope failures triggered by rainfall using
31 the Green-Ampt infiltration equation and the infinite slope stability model. This approach considers rainfall
32 intensity, soil properties, and topography. The modified Green-Ampt equation estimates rainfall infiltration
33 capacity and depth within a slope. Using the calculated infiltration depth as the slip surface depth, the factor
34 of safety is determined through the infinite slope stability model. The method also generates a time-series
35 visualization map of spatiotemporal variations in safety factors using Geographic Information System (GIS)
36 software. Chansorn et al. (28) employed a hydrological model to assess landslide occurrences within
37 Thailand's Huai Nam Phung Subbasin. By analyzing temporal changes in groundwater levels derived from
38 meteorological data using the TOPography-based hydrological MODEL (TOPMODEL), they calculated
39 slope stability safety factors at various times and locations. Their findings indicate that landslides were
40 more frequent in 2017 due to an increase in water volume from higher rainfall. The instability affected both
41 steep and gentler slopes. Cui et al. (29) explored the spatiotemporal variation of wetting front depth (WFD)
42 during rainfall episodes by considering three pore water pressure profiles with surface runoff. To account
43 for inherent uncertainty in hydrogeomechanical properties at the regional scale, they employed probabilistic
44 analysis using the recursive first-order reliability method (FORM). Their newly developed model,
45 physically based probabilistic modelling of Rainfall Landslides using Simplified Transient Infiltration
46 Model (PRL-STIM), is applied to a representative area in China that experienced extensive rainfall-induced
47 landslides. The results demonstrate the model's satisfactory prediction accuracy.

48 While numerous studies have examined rainfall-induced landslides by estimating infiltration
49 through equations or basic hydrological models, few have utilized a comprehensive hydrological model
50 that encompasses all aspects of the hydrological cycle for a more precise infiltration simulation. In this
51 study, we employed the Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT+) to simulate infiltration and runoff from

1 rainfall across the Anacostia watershed in Maryland, US, considering the entire hydrological cycle.
2 Subsequently, we developed a GIS-based model to map the minimum amount of infiltration that will cause
3 slope failure (F_{min}) and assess landslide risk, incorporating the infiltration data calculated by SWAT+. This
4 approach provides a more holistic and accurate assessment of landslide risks associated with rainfall events.

5
6 **STUDY AREA**

7 The study focuses on the Anacostia River watershed, situated in Maryland near Washington, DC.
8 It drains to the tidal portion of the Anacostia River, which joins the Potomac River portion of the
9 Chesapeake Bay (30) (Fig. 1). The Anacostia watershed covers about 178 square miles with a drainage area
10 that is 49% in Prince George’s County, Maryland, 34% in Montgomery County, Maryland, and 17% in the
11 District of Columbia (31, 32). Water residence times within the tidal Anacostia River range from 35 to 100
12 days, reflecting the substantial tidal volume relative to inflow (33). This variability in residence time plays
13 a critical role in the infiltration processes within the watershed, as it influences the movement and
14 absorption of water in urban and suburban areas.

16
17 **Figure 1. Location of the study area, Anacostia River watershed in Maryland**

18
19 The choice of this region for investigation is driven by the high frequency of historical landslides
20 in Maryland, especially in the watershed area. This selection is guided by a map, constructed using the
21 landslide inventory location data from MDOT SHA (Maryland Department of Transportation, State
22 Highway Administration). The map underscores the importance of the selected watershed for studying and
23 managing landslide events (Fig. 2).
24

Figure 2. Distributions of the historical landslides in Maryland (source: MDOT/SHA)

METHODS

Data preparation

Hydrological model data

Implementing the SWAT+ model in our study requires a thorough data collection process, focusing on detailed climate, soil, and land use specific information to the selected site. Flow rate data from USGS gauge stations in the Anacostia region is critical for model calibration. To create an accurate soil map, we utilize the USDA Soil Survey Geographic Database (SSURGO) for Maryland. Topographical features are defined using 1/3 arc-second LiDAR-based Digital Elevation Models (DEM) for Maryland. Daily weather inputs for SWAT+, including precipitation, temperature, solar radiation, relative humidity, and wind speed, are sourced from the NASA Power Larc Project for Takoma Park Station. This integration of data ensures the SWAT+ model's accuracy and reliability in simulating runoff and infiltration dynamics in the Anacostia watershed. The land use map for Maryland was obtained from the Maryland Department of Planning (MDP).

Slope stability and landslide risk data

In the study of slope instability, several key parameters are crucial. These include cohesion and the effective internal angle of friction. These parameters are based on soil types derived from the SSURGO soil map, which provides information on different soil types in various regions. The slope angle is another essential parameter for this analysis. It is obtained from DEM map using Geographic Information System (GIS) software, specifically ArcPro (Fig. 3). The bulk specific gravity (SG) of the soil is also a critical parameter. It is calculated as the ratio of the soil's unit weight to the unit weight of water and the estimation of it can also be based on the soil type and information from the soil map. On the other hand, we used the **Equation (1)** to calculate SG_{sat} (35):

$$SG_{sat} = SG + (\eta - \vartheta_{FC}) \quad (1)$$

where η is porosity and ϑ_{FC} is moisture content of soil at field capacity.

1 In some areas, soil type data might be missing. In such cases, we determined the soil type by
2 considering the percentages of clay, silt, and sand. This was done using the USGS soil type calculator. To
3 ensure a comprehensive analysis, we compiled soil properties data from various sources (Table 1). This
4 included references such as the study by Hosni et al. (36). This approach allowed us to have a thorough
5 understanding of the soil's properties, which is crucial for assessing slope instability.
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Figure 3. The slope map of Anacostia

1 **TABLE 1 Typical values of soil parameters for different soils according to USCS**

Soil type	SG	C (KN/m ²)	Phi (°)	Field capacity	Porosity	SG _{sat}
Channery loam	2.66	0	30	0.28	0.48	2.86
Channery silt loam	2.66	0	27	0.29	0.51	2.88
Clay loam	2.69	10	18	0.32	0.46	2.83
Fine sandy loam	2.64	0	33	0.15	0.46	2.95
well-graded gravel, fine to coarse gravel	2	0	40	0.08	0.36	2.28
Gravelly loam	2	0	32	0.08	0.37	2.29
Gravelly sandy loam	2	0	36	0.07	0.35	2.28
Gravelly silt loam	2	0	30	0.09	0.38	2.29
Loam	2.66	0	28	0.27	0.47	2.86
Loamy sand	2.65	0	31	0.09	0.44	3
Moderately decomposed plant material	2.2	20	17	0.32	0.47	2.35
Sand	2.65	0	37	0.17	0.43	2.91
Sandy loam	2.65	0	32	0.14	0.45	2.96
Silt loam	2.67	0	25	0.28	0.5	2.89
Silty clay loam	2.69	10	18	0.33	0.48	2.84
Slightly decomposed plant material	2.2	20	17	0.32	0.47	2.35
Silt loam highway	2.67	0	30	0.28	0.5	2.89

2

3 **Hydrological Modeling with SWAT+**

4 SWAT+ (56) is a tool created to forecast the effects of land management choices on water quality,
 5 sedimentation, and agricultural chemical levels in complex and varied watersheds over extended periods
 6 (37, 38). This widely used model has been continuously refined and improved over many years (39).
 7 SWAT+ operates on a variety of physical principles, including water and sediment flow, crop growth, and
 8 nutrient cycling, which makes it ideal for long-term studies.

9 Its flexibility is demonstrated by its ability to tackle a wide range of water resource issues,
 10 highlighting the model's comprehensive nature, strong support, and open-access source code (40).
 11 Compared to other leading hydrologic and water quality models, SWAT+ has established itself as a
 12 preferred tool in the field (38). In SWAT+ studies, maintaining the water balance is critical. The model
 13 simulates two main phases: the land phase, which controls inputs to the main channel, and the water phase,
 14 which manages movement through the watershed's channel network (41). This equation is used in SWAT+
 15 to simulate the hydrological cycle:

16

$$17 \quad SW_t = SW_0 + \sum_{i=1}^t (R_{day} - Q_{surf} - E_a - W_{seep} - Q_{gw}) \quad (2)$$

18

19 Where SW_t is the final soil water content (mm), SW_0 is the initial soil water content (mm), t is the
 20 time (day), R_{day} is the precipitation (mm), Q_{surf} is the surface runoff (mm), E_a is the evapotranspiration
 21 (mm), W_{seep} is the amount of water entering the vadose zone from the soil profile (mm), Q_{gw} and is the
 22 amount of return flow (mm).

23

24 **Calibration and model performance evaluation of SWAT+**

25 Calibration is traditionally a manual process that requires adjusting model input parameters to
 26 ensure simulated values align with measured data. However, for complex hydrologic models, the time-
 27 intensive nature of manual calibration has led to a preference for automated methods (42). Calibrating

1 SWAT+ involves numerous parameters, which adds complexity. To streamline this process, we focus on
 2 key parameters identified in prior research (42, 43, 44) for a more targeted sensitivity analysis. In this study,
 3 we used the SWATplus Toolbox and SWATplus CUP daily streamflow data from a gauge station on the
 4 Northwest branch of the Anacostia River, located at Latitude 38°57'09.2" and Longitude 76°57'54.5"
 5 (NAD83), for the period between 2015 and 2022 as our observation data to calibrate and validate the
 6 SWAT+ model.

7 There are several methods for model evaluation recommended by Moriasi et al. (45) that work well
 8 in different situations, are commonly used and accepted in published work, and have proven strengths in
 9 evaluating models. In this research, we used three of the most recommended statistical model evaluation
 10 methods: NSE, RSR, and P_{bias}.

11
 12 **Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency (NSE)** is a key statistic that tells us how much the difference between
 13 predicted and observed data compares to the variance in the measured data (45).

$$14 \quad NSE = 1 - \frac{\sum(Q_{obs} - Q_s)^2}{\sum(Q_{obs} - \bar{Q}_{obs})^2} \quad (3)$$

15
 16 Where \bar{Q}_{obs} is the mean of observed discharges, and Q_s is simulated discharge and Q_{obs} is observed
 17 discharge.

18
 19
 20 **RMSE-Observations Standard Deviation Ratio (RSR)** is a model evaluation metric introduced
 21 by Singh et al. (46). It standardizes RMSE by considering the variability in the observed data. A lower RSR
 22 generally indicates better model performance, highlighting a smaller model error relative to the variability
 23 in the measured data.

$$24 \quad RSR = \frac{RMSE}{\sigma} = \frac{\sqrt{\sum(Q_{obs} - Q_s)^2}}{\sqrt{\sum(Q_{obs} - \bar{Q}_{obs})^2}} \quad (4)$$

25
 26
 27 **Percent Bias (PBIAS)** is a metric that assesses the average tendency of simulated data to be larger
 28 or smaller than the observed data. This concept was introduced by Gupta et al. (47) in 1999. An optimal
 29 PBIAS value is 0.0, which indicates an accurate model simulation. Positive PBIAS values suggest that the
 30 model underestimates, while negative values indicate overestimation. The PBIAS is calculated using
 31 **Equation (5)**.

$$32 \quad P_{Bias} = \frac{\sum(Q_{obs} - Q_s) * 100}{\sum Q_{obs}} \quad (5)$$

33 **Slope instability physical model**

34
 35 The infinite slope method is ideal for projects that require efficient and widespread application,
 36 particularly in areas with shallow landslides triggered by rainfall (55). Since most of the slopes in Maryland
 37 are classified as shallow, based on the slope maps provided by the SHA, this research employs the infinite
 38 slope method to analyze slope instability. Applying the theory of infinite slope stability allows the
 39 identification of circumstances in which a soil layer with a thickness denoted as Z may experience sliding
 40 over a plane parallel to the surface, characterized by a slope angle of θ concerning the horizon. The criteria
 41 for sliding conditions are ascertainable through the application of Coulomb's law of friction. If seepage is
 42 presumed to be parallel to the plane of failure, the factor of safety (FS) concerning slope failure along a
 43 given plane can be computed utilizing the **Equation (6)** (48).

$$44 \quad FS = \frac{C + (\gamma_s Z - \gamma_w h) \cos^2 \theta \cdot \tan \phi}{\gamma_s Z \sin \theta \cdot \cos \theta} \quad (6)$$

Where C is the apparent cohesion, γ_s is the specific weight of soil, γ_w is the specific weight of water, h is the depth of seepage, Z is the slope thickness, θ is the slope angle, and ϕ is the effective internal angle of friction.

A factor of safety less than 1 signifies a slope failure. In particular, when the numerator of Equation (6) is smaller than its denominator, it implies that a soil layer with a thickness of Z will slip along the plane of failure (49). One approach to determine Z is by utilizing the Topographic Wetness Index (TWI), which represents moisture levels based on topography and is derived from topographic features (50). TWI can be calculated using DEM (28). The computation of TWI is outlined in **Equation (7)**.

$$TWI = \ln \frac{\alpha}{\tan \beta} \quad (7)$$

Where α is the flow accumulation and β is the slope angle (radians). The flow direction map then the TWI map can be calculated using the DEM map and by ArcGIS tools (Fig. 4). Since numerous studies have established a linear relationship between soil thickness and the TWI (51, 52, 53), this study leveraged this correlation to create soil thickness maps for Anacostia watershed. In this study, observed soil thickness was collected at 9 locations using Geosetta database. The linear relationship between these observed soil thicknesses and the TWI was then used to generate soil thickness maps using this linear equation:

$$TWI = a + b(Z) \quad (8)$$

Based on figure 5 this equation would be $Z = (TWI - 1.804) / 0.3258$ and we could generate the soil thickness map based on that.

Figure 4. The maps of flow direction and TWI of Anacostia calculated by ArcGIS

Figure 5. The linear relationship between TWI and observed slope thicknesses (Z)

After preparing Z, by expressing Equation (6) as an inequality that signifies a condition where the factor of safety is less than 1, it can be reorganized to establish the minimum depth of seepage in the soil layer essential to trigger slope failure (35). Consequently, one can ascertain the minimum seepage depth (H_{cr}) required for inducing slope failure:

$$H_{cr} = \frac{\frac{c}{\gamma_w} - SG \cdot Z \cdot \cos^2 \theta (\tan \theta - \tan \varphi)}{\cos^2 \theta [(SG_{sat} - SG)(\tan \theta - \tan \varphi) + \tan \varphi]} \quad (9)$$

Where H_{cr} is the critical seepage depth for the soil layer; SG is the bulk specific gravity of the soil, which is the ratio of the unit weight of soil to the unit weight of water; and SG_{sat} is the specific gravity of saturated soil.

Finally, with an initial moisture content at field capacity, ϑ_{FC} , and porosity (η), the minimum amount of infiltrating water (F_{min}) that will cause failure becomes:

$$F = H_{cr} \cos^2 \theta (\eta - \vartheta_{FC}) \quad (10)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hydrological model

The parameters listed in Table 2 were selected for model calibration, derived from previous research and sensitivity analysis, for the period from 2015 to 2020 (34). Some parameters, such as GW_DELAY (Groundwater Delay time) and REVAPMN (Threshold water in the shallow aquifer), which are commonly recommended in prior studies (42), showed minimal impact on simulated streamflow during our sensitivity analysis. As a result, these parameters were excluded from the calibration process. The sensitivity analysis identified SURLAG and CN2 as the most influential parameters, while Epc0 demonstrated the least sensitivity, as detailed in Table 2.

1 **TABLE 2 The results of sensitivity analysis of SWAT+ model and the value of calibrated**
 2 **parameters**

Parameter name	Description	Order sensitivity	Initial range	Final value after calibration
SURLAG	Surface runoff lag coefficient	1.95	0.05 - 24	6.146
AWC	Available water capacity of the soil layer	0.02	0.01 - 1	0.85
CN2	Curve number for moisture condition II	-0.002	(-0.2) - 0.2	0.02
Alpha	Baseflow alpha factor	-0.0065	0.01 - 1	0.191
Esco	Soil evaporation compensation factor	-0.008	0.1 - 1	0.137
Epc0	Plant uptake compensation factor	-0.0005	-	-
REVAPMN	Threshold water in shallow aquifer	0	-	-

3
 4 The comparison between simulated and observed streamflow was made at the gauge station on
 5 channel 8 of the SWAT+ model for various years between 2015 and 2020 (Figure 6). The years 2015 and
 6 2016 were used as a warm-up period. The results indicate a close match between simulated and observed
 7 flow rates. We calculated an NSE of 0.85 and Pbias of 12%, indicating very good and good performance,
 8 respectively, according to Table 3 (54). The calibrated model has an RMSE of 1.43 m³/s and an RSR of
 9 0.41, indicating very good performance. For the validation period (2021-2022), the NSE and RSR were
 10 0.68 and 0.52, respectively, indicating good performance.
 11

12 **Figure 6. Simulated and Observed streamflow at gauging station Northwest branch of Anacostia**
 13 **after calibration**
 14

1

TABLE 3 General performance ratings for NSE and RSR for a daily time step

P_{bias}	NSE	RSR	Model Performance
0-10	0.75 - 1	0 – 0.5	Very good
10-15	0.65 – 0.75	0.5 – 0.6	Good
15-20	0.5 – 0.65	0.6 – 0.7	Fair
>20	≤ 0.5	≥ 0.7	Inadequate

2

3 Figure 7 demonstrates the model's ability to quantify both surface runoff and infiltration from
 4 rainfall accurately. This capability allows precise differentiation and calculation of these volumes, ensuring
 5 an accurate assessment of hydrological processes. The model's strong performance in these simulations
 6 confirms the reliability of the results, establishing it as a robust tool for hydrological analysis and prediction.

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Figure 7. The amount of infiltration (a) and surface flow rate (b) at station of Northwest branch of Anacostia River

1 The cumulative soil moisture content shown in Figure 8 is a result from 4 days of rainfall in the
2 Anacostia watershed between December 15 and December 18, 2018. This period was selected as it includes
3 several landslide events, making it an ideal example to illustrate the spatial distribution of soil water content.
4 The map showcases the ability to simulate infiltration spatially for each rainfall event. By analyzing
5 infiltration levels across different areas of the watershed, this information can be used to create a landslide
6 risk map, aiding in the assessment of landslide potential in specific parts of the study area.

7

8 **Figure 8. Map of cumulative soil water content for 4 days in the Anacostia Watershed between**
9 **December 15 and December 18, 2018, simulated by the SWAT+ model**

1 **Landslide model**

2 Following initial modeling and testing, sensitivity analysis was conducted, resulting in Table 4.
 3 Each parameter was increased by 20%, and the corresponding change in critical seepage depth for the soil
 4 layer was calculated. Table 4 highlights the significance of SG, or bulk specific gravity of the soil, as the
 5 most influential parameter in the model. A 20% increase in SG corresponds to a 25% increase in the critical
 6 seepage depth.

7 **TABLE 4 Sensitivity analysis results**

Variable	Change in mean of Hcr (%)
Slope angle (θ)	-4.4%
Internal angle of friction (Φ)	3.0%
Cohesion (c)	1.4%
Bulk specific gravity (SG)	25.3%

8
 9 Using the collected data and values, we generated raster maps in ArcGIS by employing the "raster
 10 calculator" tool and applying equations (9) and (10). This process, applied to the first scenario, produced a
 11 map depicting the minimum amount of infiltrating water (F_{min}) in centimeters required to induce failure for
 12 a slope thickness of 1 meter, as illustrated in Figure 9. In this map, the LiDAR data, acquired from USGS
 13 has been overlaid with the output map depicting landslide risk. However, it's important to note that the
 14 LiDAR data is available only for the southern part of the study area, specifically Prince's George County.
 15 Despite this limitation, observations reveal that certain areas adjacent to historical landslide sites persist
 16 within high-risk zones as indicated by the landslide model.
 17

18
 19
 20 **Figure 9. The map of minimum amount of infiltrating water (F_{min}) that will cause failure with**
 21 **assuming slope thickness of 1 meter**

1 According to Figure 9, the red areas on the map indicate regions with a lower threshold for
2 infiltration, indicating a higher risk of landslide occurrence. Similarly, the black dots represent locations
3 of historical landslides, with many occurring in the red and orange regions, signifying elevated landslide
4 risk. This suggests that the initial landslide modeling, incorporating physical processes, is effective.

5 In the second scenario, we utilized the slope thickness map derived from the TWI method instead
6 of employing a constant soil thickness value to calculate the F_{min} map. Figure 10 illustrates the landslide
7 risk map generated using this slope thickness map. This approach allows a more accurate and detailed
8 assessment of landslide risk by incorporating variable soil thicknesses across the study area. In this map,
9 we observe that the red areas, indicating higher landslide risk, are relatively fewer and are primarily located
10 near roads.

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Figure 10. The map of minimum amount of infiltrating water (F_{min}) that will cause failure with considering slope thickness map derived from the TWI method

1 Figure 11 was created by comparing the map of the minimum amount of infiltrating water that will
2 cause failure (Figure 10) with the map of cumulative soil water content between December 15 and
3 December 18, 2018 (Figure 8). The zoomed-in section highlights two historical landslide events located in
4 high-risk areas, demonstrating the acceptable performance of the landslide model when connected to
5 simulated infiltration using the SWAT+ model.

6
7 **Figure 11. Comparison the minimum amount of infiltrating water (F_{min}) that will cause failure with**
8 **the cumulative soil water content between December 15 and December 18, 2018.**

9 **CONCLUSIONS**

10 In conclusion, this study advances the methodology for assessing landslide risks by incorporating
11 comprehensive hydrological simulations with the simplified physical model. The complex interplay
12 between infiltration and runoff, especially in regions experiencing intense precipitation events exacerbated
13 by climate change, necessitates precise modeling for effective risk assessment and mitigation. Traditional
14 methods often oversimplify infiltration estimation, leading to inaccuracies in landslide risk prediction. To
15 address this, we employed the SWAT+ model to simulate the entire hydrological cycle, focusing on the
16 Anacostia River watershed in Maryland. By integrating SWAT+ outputs with a GIS-based slope stability
17 model, we achieved a more comprehensive evaluation of landslide risks associated with rainfall events. Our
18 findings highlight the significance of detailed hydrological modeling in understanding the dynamics of
19 slope stability. The SWAT+ model's ability to simulate both surface and subsurface flow, combined with
20 precise land use, soil, and topographical data, allowed a robust analysis of infiltration and runoff. The

1 subsequent mapping of the minimum amount of infiltrating water (F_{\min}) provided a nuanced understanding
2 of landslide susceptibility across the watershed. The calibration and validation of the SWAT+ model, using
3 streamflow data from the USGS gauge station, demonstrated high model performance, reinforcing the
4 reliability of our approach. The integration of detailed soil parameters and slope stability analysis further
5 enhanced the model's predictive capability. A comparative analysis between the minimum infiltrating water
6 that will cause failure and the cumulative soil water content during a specific period highlighted two
7 historical landslide events located in high-risk areas. This comparison demonstrated the acceptable
8 performance of the landslide model when connected to simulated infiltration using the SWAT+ model.

9 In future work, we plan to further develop our hydrological and landslide models. First, we will
10 calibrate the hydrological model using flow data from more gauge stations instead of one station for a better
11 performance of the SWAT+ model. Using the calibrated SWAT+ model, we will evaluate the cumulative
12 infiltration for different durations, including 3-day, 7-day, 15-day, and monthly intervals. Additionally, we
13 will calculate the depth of groundwater (h) to incorporate into the factor of safety equation. For the landslide
14 model, we will utilize the simulated groundwater depth from the SWAT+ model to calculate the safety
15 factor of slopes, thereby enhancing the accuracy of landslide risk assessments.

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22 23 **AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS**

24 The authors confirm contribution to the paper as follows:
25 study conception and design: Hosseinizadeh and Sheng; prepare manuscript: Hosseinizadeh and Isola;
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1 REFERENCES

- 2
- 3 1. Chen, J., and Xu, C. Geological Hazards and Risk Management. *Sustainability*, 2024. 16(8), 3286.
- 4
- 5 2. U.S. Geological Survey (USGS). Landslide types and processes. Highway Research Board special
- 6 report. 2004.
- 7
- 8 3. Dani, D. E., and Stigall, A. L. Landslides: Using model-based inquiry to investigate local mass wasting
- 9 events. *Science Scope*, 2021. 44(4), 46-55.
- 10
- 11 4. Li, L., Lin, H., Qiang, Y., Zhang, Y., Liang, S., Hu, S., ... and Ni, B. Stability analysis of rainfall-
- 12 induced landslide considering air resistance delay effect and lateral seepage. *Scientific Reports*, 2024.
- 13 14(1), 8377.
- 14
- 15 5. Schuster, R. L., and Highland, L. M. Socioeconomic and environmental impacts of landslides in the
- 16 western hemisphere. 2001. (No. 2001-276).
- 17
- 18 6. UNISDR. Words into Action Guidelines: National Disaster Risk Assessment Hazard Specific Risk
- 19 Assessment 3. Landslide Hazard and Risk Assessment. 2017.
- 20
- 21 7. Emberson, R., Kirschbaum, D., and Stanley, T. New global characterisation of landslide exposure.
- 22 *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 2020. 20(12), 3413-3424.
- 23
- 24 8. Froude, M. J., and Petley, D. N. Global fatal landslide occurrence from 2004 to 2016. *Natural Hazards*
- 25 *and Earth System Sciences*, 2018. 18(8), 2161-2181.
- 26
- 27 9. Crosta, G. B., and Frattini, P. J. N. H. Distributed modelling of shallow landslides triggered by intense
- 28 rainfall. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 2003. 3(1/2), 81-93.
- 29
- 30 10. Wang, G., Li, T., Xing, X., and Zou, Y. Research on loess flow-slides induced by rainfall in July 2013
- 31 in Yan'an, NW China. *Environmental Earth Sciences*, 2015. 73, 7933-7944.
- 32
- 33 11. Zhang, Z., Zeng, R., Meng, X., Zhao, S., Wang, S., Ma, J., and Wang, H. Effects of changes in soil
- 34 properties caused by progressive infiltration of rainwater on rainfall-induced landslides. *Catena*, 2023.
- 35 233, 107475.
- 36
- 37 12. Galanti, Y., Barsanti, M., Cevasco, A., D'Amato Avanzi, G., and Giannecchini, R. Comparison of
- 38 statistical methods and multi-time validation for the determination of the shallow landslide rainfall
- 39 thresholds. *Landslides*, 2018. 15, 937-952.
- 40
- 41 13. Chen, R. H., Chen, H. P., Chen, K. S., & Zhung, H. B. Simulation of a slope failure induced by rainfall
- 42 infiltration. *Environmental Geology*, 2009. 58, 943-952.
- 43
- 44 14. Mukhlisin, M., and Taha, M. R. Numerical model of antecedent rainfall effect on slope stability at a
- 45 hillslope of weathered granitic soil formation. *Journal of the Geological Society of India*, 2012. 79,
- 46 525-531.
- 47 15. Zhang, J., Huang, H. W., Zhang, L. M., Zhu, H. H., and Shi, B. Probabilistic prediction of rainfall-
- 48 induced slope failure using a mechanics-based model. *Engineering Geology*, 2014. 168, 129-140.
- 49
- 50 16. Zhang, L., Wu, F., Zhang, H., Zhang, L., and Zhang, J. Influences of internal erosion on infiltration and
- 51 slope stability. *Bulletin of Engineering Geology and the Environment*, 2019. 78, 1815-1827.

17. Liu, Q., Su, L., Zhang, C., Hu, B., and Xiao, S. Dynamic variations of interception loss-infiltration-runoff in three land-use types and their influence on slope stability: An example from the eastern margin of the Tibetan Plateau. *Journal of Hydrology*, 2022. 612, 128218.
18. Tung, Y. K., Zhang, H., Ng, C. W. W., and Kwok, Y. F. Transient seepage analysis of rainfall infiltration using a new conjunctive surface-subsurface flow model. In Proceedings of the 57th Canadian Geotechnical Conference and the 5th Joint CGS-IAH Conference, 2004. (Vol. 7, pp. 17-22).
19. Nelson, S. A. Slope stability, triggering events, mass movement hazards. *Nat. Disasters*. 2013.
20. Wu, L. Z., Zhang, L. M., Zhou, Y., Xu, Q., Yu, B., Liu, G. G., and Bai, L. Y. Theoretical analysis and model test for rainfall-induced shallow landslides in the red-bed area of Sichuan. *Bulletin of Engineering Geology and the Environment*, 2018. 77, 1343-1353.
21. Cho, S. E., and Lee, S. R. Instability of unsaturated soil slopes due to infiltration. *Computers and geotechnics*, 2001. 28(3), 185-208.
22. Hu, W., Xu, Q., Wang, G. H., Van Asch, T. W. J., and Hicher, P. Y. Sensitivity of the initiation of debris flow to initial soil moisture. *Landslides*, 2015. 12, 1139-1145.
23. Yang, K. H., Uzuoka, R., Lin, G. L., and Nakai, Y. Coupled hydro-mechanical analysis of two unstable unsaturated slopes subject to rainfall infiltration. *Engineering Geology*, 2017. 216, 13-30.
24. Oh, S., and Lu, N. Slope stability analysis under unsaturated conditions: Case studies of rainfall-induced failure of cut slopes. *Engineering Geology*, 2015. 184, 96-103.
25. Galeandro, A., Šimůnek, J., and Simeone, V. Analysis of rainfall infiltration effects on the stability of pyroclastic soil veneer affected by vertical drying shrinkage fractures. *Bulletin of Engineering Geology and the Environment*, 2013. 72, 447-455.
26. Chiu, Y. Y., Chen, H. E., and Yeh, K. C. Investigation of the influence of rainfall runoff on shallow landslides in unsaturated soil using a mathematical model. *Water*, 2019. 11(6), 1178.
27. Dolojan, N. L. J., Moriguchi, S., Hashimoto, M., and Terada, K. Mapping method of rainfall-induced landslide hazards by infiltration and slope stability analysis: A case study in Marumori, Miyagi, Japan, during the October 2019 Typhoon Hagibis. *Landslides*, 2021. 18, 2039-2057.
28. Chansorn, R., Chotpantarat, S., and Klongvessa, P. Hydrological model of landslide risk in Huai Nam Phung subbasin, Thailand. *Bulletin of Engineering Geology and the Environment*, 2023. 82(4), 140.
29. Cui, H., Ji, J., Hürlimann, M., and Medina, V. Probabilistic and physically-based modelling of rainfall-induced landslide susceptibility using integrated GIS-FORM algorithm. *Landslides*, 2024. 21(6), 1461-1481.
30. Devereux, O. H., Prestegard, K. L., Needelman, B. A., and Gellis, A. C. Suspended-sediment sources in an urban watershed, Northeast Branch Anacostia River, Maryland. *Hydrological Processes: An International Journal*, 2010. 24(11): 1391-1403.
31. Warner, A., Shepp, D., Corish, K., and Galli, J. An existing source assessment of pollutants to the Anacostia watershed, 1997 (No. 98708).

- 1 32. Maryland Department of Natural Resources Watershed Services. Characterization Of The Anacostia
2 River Watershed In Prince George’s County, Maryland. 2005.
3
- 4 33. Hwang, H. M., and Foster, G. D. Characterization of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in urban
5 stormwater runoff flowing into the tidal Anacostia River, Washington, DC, USA. *Environmental*
6 *Pollution*, 2006. 140(3): 416-426.
7
- 8 34. Hosseinizadeh, A., Sheng, Z., Qian, S., and Liu, Y. Separating Infiltration and Runoff from
9 Precipitation over the Anacostia River Watershed, Maryland. In World Environmental and Water
10 Resources Congress, 2024. 1595-1607.
11
- 12 35. Mohseni, O., Anderson, C., Strong, M., Conway, R., Hathaway, C., Grosser, A., and Mielke, A. Storm-
13 induced slope failure susceptibility mapping, 2018. (No. MN/RC 2018-05). Minnesota. Dept. of
14 Transportation.
15
- 16 36. Hosni, A. A., Pauzi, N. I. M., and Shariffuddin, A. S. Geotechnical properties of waste soil from closed
17 construction dumping area in Serdang, Selangor, Malaysia. *Elect. J. Geotech. Eng.(EJGE)*, 17, 2015.
18
- 19 37. Williams, J. R., Arnold, J. G., Kiniry, J. R., Gassman, P. W., and Green, C. H. History of model
20 development at Temple, Texas. *Hydrological sciences journal*, 2008. 53(5), 948-960.
21
- 22 38. Gassman, P. W., Sadeghi, A. M., & Srinivasan, R. Applications of the SWAT model special section:
23 overview and insights. *Journal of Environmental Quality*, 2014. 43(1), 1-8.
24
- 25 39. Gassman, P. W., Reyes, M. R., Green, C. H., and Arnold, J. G. The soil and water assessment tool:
26 historical development, applications, and future research directions. *Transactions of the ASABE*, 2007.
27 50(4), 1211-1250.
28
- 29 40. Akoko, G., Le, T. H., Gomi, T., and Kato, T. A review of SWAT model application in Africa. *Water*,
30 2021. 13(9), 1313.
31
- 32 41. Neitsch, S. L., Arnold, J. G., Kiniry, J. R., and Williams, J. R. Soil and water assessment tool theoretical
33 documentation version 2009. Texas Water Resources Institute, 2011.
34
- 35 42. Arnold, J. G., Moriasi, D. N., Gassman, P. W., Abbaspour, K. C., White, M. J., Srinivasan, R., ... and
36 Jha, M. K. SWAT: Model use, calibration, and validation. *Transactions of the ASABE*, 2012. 55(4),
37 1491-1508.
38
- 39 43. Rostamian, R., Jaleh, A., Afyuni, M., Mousavi, S. F., Heidarpour, M., Jalalian, A., and Abbaspour, K.
40 C. Application of a SWAT model for estimating runoff and sediment in two mountainous basins in
41 central Iran. *Hydrological sciences journal*, 2008. 53(5), 977-988.
42
- 43 44. Qi, J., Lee, S., Zhang, X., Yang, Q., McCarty, G. W., and Moglen, G. E. Effects of surface runoff and
44 infiltration partition methods on hydrological modeling: A comparison of four schemes in two
45 watersheds in the Northeastern US. *Journal of Hydrology*, 2020. 581, 124415.
46
- 47 45. Moriasi, D. N., Arnold, J. G., Van Liew, M. W., Bingner, R. L., Harmel, R. D., and Veith, T. L. Model
48 evaluation guidelines for systematic quantification of accuracy in watershed simulations. *Transactions*
49 *of the ASABE*, 2007. 50(3), 885-900.
50

- 1 46. Singh, J., Knapp, H.V., and Demissie, M. Hydrologic Modeling of the Iroquois River Watershed Using
2 HSPF and SWAT. Illinois Department of Natural Resources and the Illinois State Geological Survey,
3 2004. Illinois State Water Survey Contract Report 2004-08.
4
- 5 47. Gupta, H. V., Sorooshian, S., and Yapo, P. O. Status of automatic calibration for hydrologic models:
6 Comparison with multilevel expert calibration. *Journal of hydrologic engineering*, 1999. 4(2), 135-143.
7
- 8 48. Skempton, A. W., and DeLory, F. A. Stability of natural slopes in London clay. In Selected Papers on
9 Soil Mechanics, 1984. (pp. 70-73). Thomas Telford Publishing.
10
- 11 49. Xiao, S., Dai, T., and Li, S. Review and Comparative Analysis of Factor of Safety Definitions in Slope
12 Stability. *Geotechnical and Geological Engineering*, 2024. 1-21.
13
- 14 50. Moore, I. D., Gessler, P. E., Nielsen, G. A. E., and Peterson, G. A. Soil attribute prediction using terrain
15 analysis. *Soil science society of america journal*, 1993. 57(2), 443-452.
16
- 17 51. Lee, K. T., and Ho, J. Y. Prediction of landslide occurrence based on slope-instability analysis and
18 hydrological model simulation. *Journal of Hydrology*, 2009. 375(3-4), 489-497.
19
- 20 52. Ho, J. Y., Lee, K. T., Chang, T. C., Wang, Z. Y., and Liao, Y. H. Influences of spatial distribution of
21 soil thickness on shallow landslide prediction. *Engineering Geology*, 2012. 124, 38-46.
22
- 23 53. Olyphant, J., Pelletier, J. D., and Johnson, R. Topographic correlations with soil and regolith thickness
24 from shallow-seismic refraction constraints across upland hillslopes in the Valles Caldera, New
25 Mexico. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, 2016. 41(12), 1684-1696.
26
- 27 54. Cardoso de Salis, H. H., Monteiro da Costa, A., Moreira Vianna, J. H., Azeneth Schuler, M., Künne,
28 A., Sanches Fernandes, L. F., and Leal Pacheco, F. A. Hydrologic modeling for sustainable water
29 resources management in urbanized karst areas. *International journal of environmental research and
30 public health*, 2019. 16(14), 2542.
31
- 32 55. Abramson, L. W., Lee, T. S., Sharma, S., and Boyce, G. M. Slope stability and stabilization methods.
33 John Wiley & Sons. 2001.
34
- 35 56. SWAT+ model link: <https://swat.tamu.edu/software/plus/>
36
- 37 57. Liu, Q. Q., and Li, J. C. Effects of water seepage on the stability of soil-slopes. *Procedia IUTAM*, 2015.
38 17, 29-39.
39
40